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Creating virtual and real consumer experiences to identify consumer preferences and perceptions to design intervention strategies

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List of abbreviations

ASC – Alternative Specific Constant

AIC – Akaike information criterion

BIC – Bayesian information criterion

DCE – Discrete Choice Experiment

EU – European Union

GOF – Goodness of Fit

IIA – Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives

MNL – Multinomial Logit

MOA – Motivation-Opportunity-Ability

QDA – Quantitative Descriptive Analysis

WP – Work Package

WTP – Willingness to Pay

Executive summary

The *FishEUTrust* Work Package 2 (WP2) designs and validates a tailored set of interventions to increase consumer consumption and trust of seafood products produced in the European Union (EU). This will enable the project partners to define and develop effective strategies to promote the uptake of *FishEUTrust* products.

This deliverable presents Task 2.3 outcomes, which consist of a series of behavioral experiments testing consumer responses to different aspects of seafood products, based on information on consumer clusters and behaviors gathered in Task 2.1 and 2.2. These experiments investigate consumer inclinations towards environmental impact, label details, production origin and animal welfare, among others. Task 2.3 findings offer insight into how consumers make choices in immersive and realistic scenarios and inform future engagement strategies in the *FishEUTrust* project.

The report's first chapter describes the activities of Tasks 2.1 and 2.2, outlining the connection with Task 2.3, and anticipating the expected results of the final deliverable. The following section describes the methodology adopted in Task 2.3, the experiments, and introduces the different methods that have intersected this project, namely:

- Discrete Choice experiments (DCE): it is a widely used technique, enabling the understanding of consumer preferences and decision-making processes. In the *FishEUTrust* Project it was used to let participants choose between different product options, varying in attributes. This had the goal of understanding which features influenced purchasing decisions the most. The peculiarity of this study is that it approached DCE by designing an immersive virtual environment in which to conduct the choice experiments, in a realistic but controlled setting. This helped simulate a shopping experience where participants interacted with digital seafood, choosing in a way that reflects real-life behavior.
- Sensory analysis: it is a method that investigates how people perceive food products through their senses (i.e., taste, smell, appearance and texture). This is used to assess how sensory characteristics influence consumer preferences, satisfaction and willingness to purchase.

The methodology adopted in *FishEUTrust* represents an innovative approach to investigating consumer preferences by integrating two complementary methods, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the factors influencing consumer choice. Data have been collected in Italy and Slovenia, with collection in Denmark planned for a subsequent research phase.

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1. Introduction

According to the EU Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (2021), 60% of EU citizens consume or purchase fishery or aquaculture products at least once per month. Aquaculture also plays a significant role in EU seafood production, accounting for 26.9% (1.09 of 4.05 million tons) in 2020 (FAO, 2022). Despite this, farmed seafood remains less accepted than wild-caught products. In 2021, 32% of EU respondents expressed a preference for wild seafood, while only 7% preferred farmed alternatives (European Commission, 2021).

Information on farmed fish remains fragmented and lacks a comprehensive approach, hindering consumer understanding and acceptance. Both scientists and policymakers agree on the need to highlight the industry's environmental and social values to improve product transparency and traceability. A general lack of trust persists, fueled by limited information on fishing methods, feed, animal welfare, processing, and transport.

To make EU aquaculture more sustainable, it is essential to stimulate consumer demand for farmed seafood and rebuild trust. Identifying the drivers and barriers influencing consumer choices regarding sustainable aquaculture products is key to designing effective, consumer-focused market and policy interventions.

The core innovation of *FishEUTrust* lies in integrating stakeholders, industry actors, and consumer groups through a unified platform. This initiative brings together technology providers, supply chain stakeholders, and policy actors to co-develop tools, systems, and protocols across the seafood value chain, with the goal of enhancing consumer awareness, engagement, and trust.

1.1 Insights from FishEUTrust consumer research

FishEUTrust Task 2.1 focused on mapping consumer expectations by identifying key drivers and barriers across EU countries through a literature review and stakeholder interviews. Drivers and barriers identified in the literature were classified using the Motivation-Opportunity-Ability (MOA) behavioral framework (Rothschild 1999; MacInnis, Moorman, and Jaworski 1991). *Motivation* refers to an individual's intention to act; *Opportunity* denotes access to external material and non-material resources (e.g., time, technology, infrastructure) that enable action; and *Ability* relates to the individual's knowledge and skills required to carry out the behavior. The review included 73 grey literature sources and 70 scientific publications. Additionally, 14 online interviews were conducted with stakeholders from three geographic areas to enrich and validate the literature findings.

Among the key drivers and barriers identified in Task 2.1, *price* emerged as a major factor influencing seafood purchases. Its impact varies with socio-demographic characteristics, acting as either a driver or a barrier depending on consumer income and occupation. Health concerns also ranked among the most significant drivers of fish consumption.

Additional drivers and barriers include fish sensory attributes, freshness, quality, safety, origin, labelling and certification, sustainability and environmental concerns, production method, and consumer trust. Task 2.1 also revealed that these factors do not influence all consumer groups equally, with variation across gender, age, education, income, and family structure (Figure 1). This segmentation was further explored in Task 2.2, which focused on identifying distinct consumer profiles.

Task 2.2 aimed to identify consumer profiles sharing similar characteristics. The analysis was conducted in three countries representing different European regions: Italy (Southern Europe), Slovenia (Central Europe), and Denmark (Northern Europe).

Figure 1.1: Identified drivers and barriers to seafood consumption

Motivation	Opportunity	Ability
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attitudes towards farmed fish • Beliefs on dangers of aquaculture • Concern about <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Animal welfare</i> • <i>Environmental impacts</i> • <i>Health</i> • <i>Production methods</i> • Cultural and social norms • Lifestyle/Dietary reasons • Luxury taste/Status symbol • Trust in industry actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Types of fish</i> • <i>Reliable references</i> • Availability of wild fish • Brand • Origin <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Local, national, imported</i> • Occasion for consumption • Presentation of the product • Price • Place of purchase 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Culture and habits • Certification & Labeling • Food literacy • Information provided by media • Knowledge of fisheries • Self-efficacy and convenience • Sensory properties & Organoleptics
Socio-Demographics		
Age, Education level, Gender, Household structure, Household income, Place of residence		

Task 2.2 further identified consumer clusters based on declared seafood preferences, purchasing behaviour, and knowledge. Thirteen profiles were defined: five in Italy, and four each in Denmark and Slovenia. While each profile exhibits distinct patterns, some cross-country trends emerged. Most consumers prefer wild over farmed fish, although some groups showed no strong preference—indicating potential market opportunities for aquaculture products. Among the most important drivers and barriers for fish consumption, *price* appeared to be the most relevant factor for all groups, especially for low-income clusters who tend to buy less fish and more often consume frozen or canned products. *Freshness* and *quality* were also identified as strong drivers across almost all consumer types. Interestingly, several "health-oriented" groups were found in all countries, showing a potential for communication strategies focusing on seafood health benefits. Knowledge of aquaculture and related labels remains limited. Although highly educated consumers report greater awareness, they are also more prone to believing *misleading information* about aquaculture's environmental impacts. Overall, a negative perception of aquaculture persists among a significant share of consumers. This underscores the need for accurate, targeted communication to enhance acceptance of sustainable and safe aquaculture products. These insights informed the experimental activities in Task 2.3, which are further developed in this report.

The following sections summarize the final cluster analysis results by country.

1.1.1 Denmark

The largest cluster of Danish consumers identified in the analysis prioritizes *health benefits* and *sustainability* when purchasing fish products (Figure 1.2). *Price* was not a primary factor for this group, suggesting that other values more strongly influence their food choices. Additionally, a smaller yet notable cluster preferred *farmed over wild fish*. This group included the highest-income respondents in the Danish sample, indicating that favorable attitudes toward aquaculture may be linked to socioeconomic status in certain contexts.

Figure 1.2: Consumer profiles in Denmark

1.1.2 Italy

The largest consumer cluster appears familiar with aquaculture and its products (Figure 1.3). Members of this group show high consumption standards and generally prefer *wild fish* over *farmed fish* alternatives. A smaller but notable cluster prioritizes *country of origin*. Although *wild fish* remains the preferred option across most groups, *wild* and *farmed fish* are perceived similarly by many, indicating a potential openness to aquaculture among a significant share of consumers.

Figure 1.3: Consumer profiles in Italy

1.1.3 Slovenia

Wild fish is generally preferred over *farmed fish*; however, a consistent level of indifference between the two is observed across all clusters. The largest share of consumers appears unfamiliar with aquaculture and prioritizes *price* and *ease of preparation* in purchasing decisions (Figure 1.4). While *wild fish* is typically favored, many consumers express no strong preference, reinforcing the mixed perception and potential openness toward aquaculture products. Overall, approximately two-thirds of Slovenian consumers focus on *price* and *cooking convenience*, while the remaining third places greater importance on attributes such as *origin* and *sustainability*.

Figure 1.4: Consumer profiles in Slovenia

1.2 The FishEUTrust experiment

Building on the findings of Tasks 2.1 and 2.2, this report assesses consumer awareness and acceptance of seafood products by analyzing decision-making processes and sensory preferences. The assessment employed a virtual Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) combined with a sensory evaluation involving four seafood products. Attribute selection was guided by the MOA (Motivation-Opportunity-Ability) framework, addressing both exogenous (Opportunity) and endogenous (Ability) factors as defined earlier in the project.

The four products—sea bream, turbot, trout, and mussels—were selected for their distinct characteristics and representation of different seafood market segments. This diversity reflects varying consumer access (Opportunity) and perception across countries and profiles. Consumer preferences were evaluated based on a set of attributes, including product form (whole raw fish, fillets or cleaned shellfish, frozen, ready-to-cook), expiration date (short or long), origin (EU vs. extra-EU), and labelling (brand of producer, organic certification, sustainable aquaculture label, certified supply chain logo).

Findings from this research will inform the identification of product features that most influence consumer choices. These insights will support the development of effective strategies to increase awareness and demand for aquaculture products, as targeted in *FishEUTrust* Task 2.4.

2. Methodology

This study adopts a mixed-method approach to analyze EU consumer preferences, combining a virtual Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) with a real-life tasting experience. This innovative design helps mitigate biases associated with each of the two methods, when used alone. This section

presents the main methodological features and details the data collection process, which involved 50 adult consumers (aged 18–65) in Italy and 51 in Slovenia.

2.1 Discrete Choice experiments

DCEs are widely used to elicit consumer preferences and assess how individuals value different product or service attributes. By presenting a series of hypothetical alternatives varying across specific characteristics, DCEs enable researchers to analyse decision-making and quantify the relative importance of product features.

DCEs are grounded in Lancaster's Economic Theory of Value (Lancaster, 1966), which posits that consumer utility derives not from the product itself, but from its attributes. They also rely on Random Utility Theory (McFadden, 1974), which assumes that individuals act rationally, selecting the alternative which maximizes their utility. This utility comprises both an observable component—related to product attributes—and an unobservable component, reflecting individual preferences or motivations. For example, a consumer may choose a more expensive organic option due to personal values tied to sustainability, even if such motivations are not explicitly captured.

The preferences elicited through DCEs are known as stated preferences, as they are directly reported by respondents when choosing among hypothetical options. This method is especially valuable when market data is unavailable or when exploring preferences for new or unfamiliar products. In contrast, revealed preferences are derived from observed real-world behaviour, such as actual purchasing data.

The structure of a DCE includes two essential components:

- Choice Sets: in a DCE, participants are presented with sets of alternatives from which they must select their preferred option. Each set typically includes no more than five alternatives to ensure cognitive manageability. Most DCE designs include between 8 and 10 choice sets per respondent.
- Attributes and Levels: attributes are the key characteristics of a product or service varied systematically in a DCE, while levels represent the specific values these attributes can take. DCEs allow for the estimation of the relative importance of each attribute and the utility derived from each level.

DCEs are traditionally conducted through surveys; however, emerging approaches increasingly leverage immersive technologies, such as virtual environments, to enhance realism, reduce cognitive load, and mitigate biases associated with conventional formats.

A key limitation of survey-based DCEs is their reliance on participant mental visualization of options, which may introduce bias and reduce response reliability. Virtual and immersive technologies address this by providing realistic, intuitive environments that foster natural engagement and improve data quality. This helps narrow the gap between stated and revealed preferences by enabling decision-making in lifelike contexts.

2.2 Virtual Discrete Choice Experiments

Virtual Discrete Choice Experiments (DCEs) are conducted in computer-mediated synthetic environments that participants experience through immersive tools such as virtual visors. These environments simulate real-world settings via sensory stimuli—typically visual, and often auditory (Fiore et al., 2009). Compared to traditional survey-based methods, virtual DCEs offer distinct advantages in studying consumer preferences. Their primary strength lies in the heightened

realism and engagement they provide. By interacting with a simulated environment, participants make decisions more naturally, and researchers can collect additional behavioral data, including decision times and navigation patterns. The immersive nature of virtual DCEs also enhances experimental control and participant involvement, as immersion fosters a stronger sense of presence, which standardizes stimuli and promotes deeper engagement (Cummings and Bailenson, 2016). This “being there” effect can elicit unconscious physiological responses (Mokas et al., 2021), offering researchers richer behavioral insights based on the perceived realism of the environment.

Virtual DCEs are particularly effective in reducing hypothetical bias by simulating realistic decision-making contexts (Fang et al., 2021). Their validity is increasingly supported in the literature, especially in domains such as food choice (Xu, Siegrist, & Hartmann, 2021), tourism, and landscape valuation (Calisto & Sarkar, 2024; van Vliet et al., 2020). Additionally, they allow for the efficient testing of multiple attributes and levels at relatively low cost, offering economies of scale. The flexibility of virtual platforms also facilitates interdisciplinary collaboration, enabling researchers to co-design complex experiments and simulate scenarios that are otherwise difficult to replicate. These tools provide enhanced control over experimental variables. However, they are not suited for replicating simple real-world contexts—such as store shelving—that can be more accurately studied offline. Technological integration further strengthens virtual DCEs. The use of multimedia elements (e.g., video, ambient sound) and biometric tools such as eye-tracking enhances realism and supports the collection of rich, multi-dimensional behavioral data.

Nonetheless, virtual DCEs have limitations, particularly in food-related research. They cannot assess organoleptic properties such as taste or smell, and the absence of physical interaction restricts the observation of non-verbal cues. Simulating complex environmental stimuli, like social dynamics or background noise, also remains challenging. To address these gaps, *FishEUTrust* adopted a hybrid protocol combining a virtual DCE with real-life sensory evaluation, as described in the following section. This approach aimed to enhance realism, support fuller participant engagement, and yield more reliable insights into consumer preferences.

2.3 Sensory analysis

The sensory analysis was conducted in two phases: an expert evaluation followed by consumer testing with participants from the Virtual DCE. In the first phase, a panel of six expert assessors was selected, trained, and qualified according to ISO 8586 standards. Assessors underwent a targeted training program, including calibration sessions and familiarization with the seafood matrices under study, to harmonize their sensory acuity and descriptive consistency. This process minimized individual variability and ensured data reliability. The panel then performed a Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) (Stone et al., 2004) on four selected products—turbot, trout, seabream, and mussels. This method generated standardized sensory profiles based on key attributes such as appearance, odor, texture, taste, and aftertaste. These profiles formed the objective basis for analyzing consumer hedonic responses in the second phase.

The second phase involved the same consumers who participated in the Virtual DCE. Each participant tasted one sample of each product, cooked in individual glass containers without added salt, fats, or seasonings, to ensure standardization and minimize external sensory influences. Following each tasting, participants completed a questionnaire assessing product liking, purchase intention, and willingness to pay a premium over the standard market price.

2.4 The FishEUTrust experiment

This section outlines the experimental phases, which involved six expert panelists, 50 consumers in Italy (Cesenatico), and 51 in Slovenia (Ljubljana). Activities were conducted in the local language or in English. Participants received electronic vouchers as compensation. The study was approved by the Bioethics Committee of the University of Bologna (authorization no. 0124278, issued on April 23, 2025).

The objective was to investigate consumer preferences across four fish types, each representing a distinct segment of the European seafood market:

- Sea Bream: a medium-to-high quality saltwater fish; widely consumed
- Turbot: a high-quality saltwater fish, with superior organoleptic properties and higher prices; a niche product
- Trout: a medium-quality freshwater fish; widely consumed
- Mussels: one of the most widely consumed mollusks

Preferences for each product were evaluated with respect to four attributes, each with specific levels. Table 2.1 summarizes product attributes investigated. The first attribute, *preparation* (whole fish, fresh fillet or cleaned shellfish, frozen, ready-to-cook), relates to the *Opportunity* construct of the MOA framework. It reflects consumers' practical preferences and perceived ease of use—factors previously identified as key behavioral barriers and facilitators.

The second attribute, *expiration date* (short, long), addresses broader concerns about food waste and sustainability. It assesses whether consumers are open to purchasing products nearing expiry or if short shelf life deters selection regardless of other traits.

The third attribute, *origin* (EU, extra-EU), also pertains to the *Opportunity* construct. While not equally relevant across all consumer clusters, origin has been widely cited in the literature as influencing trust and perceptions of quality and sustainability.

The fourth attribute, *label* (brand of producer, organic certification, sustainable aquaculture label, certified supply chain logo), is linked to the *Ability* construct. Deliverable 2.1 highlighted a gap between the perceived value of labels and actual understanding. By varying the level of information, the experiment tested whether labels serve primarily as reassurance cues or facilitate more informed decisions.

Price was intentionally excluded from the experimental design, as its dominant influence on consumer choices could have overshadowed the assessment of other attributes.

Table 2.1: Attributes and levels in the Virtual DCE

Attribute	Levels			
	Sea Bream	Trout	Turbot	Mussels
Preparation	Whole, raw, clean	Fresh, cleaned (e.g. fresh fillet)	Frozen	Ready to cook
Origin	EU	Extra-EU		
Expiration Date	Short	Long		
Label	Sustainable aquaculture	Certified supply chain	Organic label	Brand of Producer

An orthogonal design approach was used to determine the number of choice sets, ensuring that each pair of attribute levels appeared with equal frequency across combinations (Johnson et al., 2013). This method enabled the creation of distinct and statistically independent choice sets. After defining the attribute-level combinations for each product and choice set, corresponding 3D objects were developed and integrated into the virtual environment for the DCE. Two-dimensional representations of the products and labels are provided in Appendix 1.

A total of 16 choice sets were created and divided into two blocks of eight. Each participant was exposed to one block, minimizing respondent burden while ensuring full coverage of all product combinations across the sample (Reed Johnson et al., 2013). The first phase of data collection involved the Virtual DCE. Participants received written instructions beforehand and used a Meta Quest 3 headset (Figure 2.1), preloaded with the *FishEUTrust* virtual environment. A researcher supervised each session, providing verbal guidance, ensuring proper device use, and safeguarding participant safety.

Figure 2.1: A participant in the experiment

The virtual environment featured a desk within a neutral setting, where each choice set—comprising three alternative products—was displayed. To begin, participants were instructed to press a blue virtual button, allowing them to acclimate to the environment. After holding the button for a few seconds, the first choice set appeared (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Experiment introduction and visualization choice set (English version)

Consumers picked up and examined the products, then selected one by placing it in a virtual cart (Figure 2.3). Upon selection, a panel displaying relevant product information appeared. After each choice, the unselected products disappeared, and the next choice set appeared on the desk.

Figure 2.3: Information panel and cart (English version)

After the eighth choice, a summary panel displayed all selected options along with a randomly generated four-digit code. Participants communicated this code to a research team member, who recorded it on a label; participants also wrote the code on the survey completed after the sensory analysis. This procedure ensured data from the Virtual DCE and sensory evaluation could be matched anonymously, preventing personal identification.

The second phase involved sensory analysis, where consumers tasted samples of each seafood product and evaluated taste, texture, and appearance. They then completed a survey rating their liking, purchase likelihood, and premium price willingness compared to market prices. In the final phase, participants completed a questionnaire on socio-demographic details including age, gender, employment, income, household size, residence, and distance from the coast.

2.5 Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted in three steps. The first step involved descriptive statistics on socio-demographic characteristics and declared habits related to meal preparation, seafood purchasing, and aquaculture product use. The second step analyzed Virtual DCE results using a Multinomial Logit (MNL) model, also known as the Conditional Logit model (McFadden, 1974). The MNL relates the probability of choosing among alternatives to the attributes describing them. The model assumes rational choices where utility from each alternative is a linear function of its attributes. MNL is straightforward to estimate (Hauber et al. 2016) and aligns with Random Utility Theory. MNL relies on the Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA) property, meaning the odds of choosing one option over another are unaffected by other alternatives in the choice set. Mathematically, the model is expressed as:

$$\frac{P(i)}{P(j)} = e^{(V_i - V_j)}$$

where $P(i)$ and $P(j)$ are the probabilities of choosing alternatives i and j , and V_i and V_j are their deterministic utilities.

The final phase involved descriptive analysis of sensory evaluation results from expert panelists and survey responses collected after the sensory test. The next section presents and discusses experiment results.

3. Results and discussion

This section analyzes data from participants in Italy (n=50), Slovenia (n=51), and the combined sample (n=101). It explores socio-demographic patterns, purchasing behavior, and sensory preferences. Subsections include descriptive statistics, purchasing frequency analysis, degustation results (sensory evaluation and purchase intent), and estimation of a Multinomial Logit model (MNL) to identify factors influencing choices.

3.1 Socio-demographic characteristics

The socio-demographic profile of participants was investigated through a questionnaire covering gender, age, education, occupation, income, family composition, residential area, and distance from the coast. About 60% were female, with a higher share in Slovenia (65%) than Italy (54%). Nearly 70% were aged 18–35, with no participants over 66. Most had a university degree and were full-time employed or students.

Around 80% reported a net monthly income between €1,500 and €7,500. Large families and households with children under 18 were uncommon, reflecting the young adult sample. Most lived in urban areas, while nearly half resided far from the coast, typically a 1–2 hour travel distance. Table 3.1 presents the socio-demographic survey findings.

Table 3.1: Sample socio-demographical characteristics

ITEM	GENERAL		ITALY		SLOVENIA	
	Respondents (n = 101)		Respondents (n = 50)		Respondents (n = 51)	
Gender						
Male	41	40.59%	23	46%	18	35.29%
Female	60	59.41%	27	54%	33	64.71%
Prefer not to say	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Age						
18 – 25	25	24.75%	9	18%	16	31.37%
26 – 35	44	43.56%	25	50%	19	37.25%
36 – 45	15	14.85%	7	14%	8	15.69%
46 – 55	7	6.93%	3	6%	4	7.84%
56 – 65	10	9.90%	6	12%	4	7.84%
66 or above	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Education level:						
Elementary school or below	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
Middle school diploma	13	12.87%	1	2%	12	23.53%
High school diploma	15	14.85%	10	20%	5	9.80%
Bachelor's or master's degree	49	48.51%	26	52%	23	45.10%
Postgraduate degree or PhD	23	22.77%	13	26%	10	19.61%
Main occupation:						
Self-employed with employees	3	2.97%	3	6%	0	0%
Self-employed without employees	7	6.93%	5	10%	2	3.92%
Full-time employee	54	53.47%	19	38%	35	68.63%
Part-time employee	4	3.96%	4	8%	0	0%
Seasonal/temporary worker	1	0.99%	1	2%	0	0%
Full-time homemaker	2	1.98%	2	4%	0	0%
Full-time student	25	24.75%	12	24%	13	25.49%
Unemployed	3	2.97%	3	6%	0	0%
Retired	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Other (please specify)	2	1.98%	1	2%	1	1.96%
Net monthly income (in EUR):						
Less than 1,500	12	11.88%	9	18%	3	5.88%
Between 1,500 and 3,000	34	33.66%	16	32%	18	35.29%
Between 3,000 and 7,500	45	44.55%	17	34%	28	54.90%
More than 7,500	4	3.96%	3	6%	1	1.96%
I don't know / Prefer not to answer	6	5.94%	5	10%	1	1.96%
Household size:						
1	17	16.83%	12	24%	5	9.80%
2	32	31.68%	14	28%	18	35.29%
3	26	25.74%	13	26%	13	25.49%
4	18	17.82%	8	16%	10	19.61%
≥ 5	8	7.92%	3	6%	5	9.80%

Family members < 18 y.o.:						
0	77	76.24%	41	82%	36	70.59%
1	11	10.89%	3	6%	8	15.69%
2	10	9.90%	5	10%	5	9.80%
≥ 3	3	2.97%	1	2%	2	3.92%
Residential area:						
Metropolitan City (At least 1 million inhabitants)	1	0.99%	1	2%	0	0%
Large City (100,000 - 1 million inhabitants)	36	35.64%	13	26%	23	45.10%
City (20,000 - 100,000 inhabitants)	32	31.68%	26	52%	6	11.76%
Small Town (10,000 - 20,000 inhabitants)	8	7.92%	6	12%	2	3.92%
Village (5,000 - 10,000 inhabitants)	6	5.94%	2	4%	4	7.84%
Rural Area (Fewer than 5,000 inhabitants)	18	17.82%	2	4%	16	31.37%
Distance between residence and the coast:						
I live right on / near the coast	20	19.80%	19	38%	1	1.96%
I live close to the coast (Less than 30 minutes to reach it)	9	8.91%	9	18%	0	0%
I live somewhat far from the coast (30 minutes to 1 hour to reach it)	23	22.77%	11	22%	12	23.53%
Quite far (1 to 2 hours to reach it)	47	46.53%	10	20%	37	72.55%
Very far (More than 2 hours to reach it)	2	1.98%	1	2%	1	1.96%

3.2 Seafood purchasing and preparation frequency

The present subsection assesses how often participants buy general food products, prepare meals for their families, and specifically purchase seafood (fish and shellfish), as well as aquaculture products. These responses offer insights into consumption patterns and preferences affecting market demand, particularly for fish and farmed shellfish.

When asked, "How often do you buy food for your family?", 50% said more than half the time, more common in Italy than Slovenia. Around 30% reported about half the time, and 19% less than half the time. Table 3.2 shows absolute numbers and percentages by country, while Figure 3.1 displays percentage distributions.

Table 3.2: Frequency of family food purchases

How often do you buy food products for your family?	General n (%)	Italy n (%)	Slovenia n (%)
Less than half the time	19 (18.81%)	7 (14%)	12 (23.53%)
About half the time	30 (29.70%)	13 (26%)	17 (33.33%)
More than half the time	51 (50.50%)	30 (60%)	21 (41.18%)
I don't know / Prefer not to answer	1 (0.99%)	0 (0%)	1 (1.96%)
Total	101 (100%)	50 (100%)	51 (100%)

Figure 3.1: Distribution of family food purchases frequency

When asked, “How often do you prepare meals for your family?”, nearly half of the respondents (46.53%) reported preparing meals more than half the time, while another significant portion (33.66%) indicated they do so about half the time. These results highlight strong and consistent involvement in meal preparation across both countries. Detailed counts (n) and percentages (%) by response category are provided in Table 3.3 and visually represented in Figure 3.2 for easier comparison.

Table 3.3: Frequency of meal preparation

How often do you prepare meals for your family?	General n (%)	Italy n (%)	Slovenia n (%)
Less than half the time	19 (18.81%)	10 (20%)	9 (17.65%)
About half the time	34 (33.66%)	12 (24%)	22 (43.14%)
More than half the time	47 (46.53%)	28 (56%)	19 (37.25%)
I don't know / Prefer not to answer	1 (0.99%)	0	1 (1.96%)
Total	101 (100%)	50 (100%)	51 (100%)

Figure 3.2 Distribution of family meal preparation frequency

Participants generally purchase seafood products (fish and shellfish) several times per week or month. Fewer than 5% buy seafood less frequently, and none reported daily or near-daily purchases. [Table 3.4](#) shows counts and percentages, while [Figure 3.3](#) visualizes the data by country.

Table 3.4: Frequency of seafood product purchase

Please indicate how often you buy seafood products (fish and shellfish)	General n (%)	Italy n (%)	Slovenia n (%)
Never	5 (4.95%)	4 (8%)	1 (1.96%)
Once a month or less	22 (21.78%)	8 (16%)	14 (27.45%)
2-3 times a month	35 (34.65%)	18 (36%)	17 (33.33%)
Once a week	25 (24.75%)	12 (24%)	13 (25.49%)
2-3 times a week	14 (13.86%)	8 (16%)	6 (11.76%)
Every day or almost every day	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
I don't know / Prefer not to answer	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Total	101 (100%)	50 (100%)	51 (100%)

Figure 3.3 Frequency of seafood product purchases

Participants generally purchase aquaculture products (farmed fish or shellfish) several times per week or month, similar to overall seafood buying patterns. However, nearly 22% reported never purchasing aquaculture products. [Table 3.5](#) shows counts and percentages, and [Figure 3.4](#) compares Italian and Slovenian data.

Table 3.5: Frequency of aquaculture product (farmed fish and shellfish) purchases

Please indicate how often you buy aquaculture products (farmed fish or shellfish)	General	Italy	Slovenia
Never	22 (21.78%)	7 (14%)	15 (29.41%)
Once a month or less	37 (36.63%)	18 (36%)	19 (37.25%)
2-3 times a month	17 (16.83%)	9 (18%)	8 (15.69%)
Once a week	14 (13.86%)	10 (20%)	4 (7.84%)
2-3 times a week	2 (1.98%)	1 (2%)	1 (1.96%)
Every day or almost every day	0	0	0
I don't know / Prefer not to answer	9 (8.91%)	5 (10%)	4 (7.84%)
Total	101 (100%)	50 (100%)	51 (100%)

Figure 3.4: Frequency of aquaculture product (farmed fish and shellfish) purchases

3.3 Analysis of consumer preferences for aquaculture products

This section presents the Multinomial Logit (MNL) model results, including goodness-of-fit, estimated coefficients, and visualizations. The model used data from 101 respondents, yielding 2,424 possible choice combinations (1,200 Italy; 1,224 Slovenia), calculated as respondents (101) × choice tasks (8) × alternatives per task (3). Of these, 808 choices were observed (400 Italy, 408 Slovenia).

The MNL estimated coefficients for 16 levels across five attributes. Since no opt-out was available, no Alternative Specific Constant (ASC) was included. The first level of each attribute (e.g., "Sea Bream" for species, "Whole fish" for preparation, "EU" for origin, "Short" for expiration, and "Sustainable Aquaculture" for labeling) was the reference category, with coefficients normalized to zero. Coefficients indicate relative preference versus the reference. Positive values show increased choice likelihood; negative values show decreased preference. Standard errors reflect uncertainty, and p-values ($p < 0.05$) denote statistical significance.

Results (Table 3.6, Figure 3.5) show the highest positive coefficient for “Brand of producer” (0.219), reflecting strong preference for labeled products. Turbot also had a positive coefficient (0.132), preferred over Sea Bream. The most negative and significant coefficients were for “Ready to cook” (-0.612) and “Frozen” (-0.461), indicating strong aversion to processed fish compared to whole fish.

Table 3.6: Multinomial Logit model coefficients

Level	General model Coefficients (s.e.)	Italy model Coefficients (s.e.)	Slovenia model Coefficients (s.e.)
Specimen			
Sea Bream	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Trout	-0.025 (0.108)	-0.319 ** (0.155)	0.260* (0.156)
Turbot	0.132 (0.107)	0.002 (0.148)	0.278* (0.158)
Mussels	-0.309 ** (0.114)	-0.415 ** (0.158)	-0.216 (0.168)
Preparation			
Whole fish	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Fresh cleaned	-0.173* (0.103)	0.014 (0.144)	-0.364 ** (0.148)
Frozen	-0.461 *** (0.107)	-0.535 *** (0.156)	-0.410 ** (0.149)
Ready to cook	-0.612 *** (0.110)	-0.541 *** (0.156)	-0.683 *** (0.160)
Origin			
EU	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Extra EU	-0.143* (0.077)	-0.039 (0.110)	-0.248 ** (0.110)
Expiration date			
Short	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Long	-0.163 ** (0.078)	-0.014 (0.111)	-0.304 ** (0.112)
Label			
Sustainable aquaculture	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Certified supply chain	-0.097 (0.109)	0.020 (0.157)	-0.209 (0.153)
Organic label	-0.298 *** (0.113)	-0.078 (0.161)	-0.531 *** (0.164)
Brand of producer	0.219 ** (0.105)	0.271* (0.105)	0.152 (0.148)

Significance level: $p < 0.001$ '***'; $p < 0.05$ '**'; $p < 0.1$ '*'; ref=reference

These patterns are consistent across the country-specific models for Italy and Slovenia, though the magnitude and significance of coefficients vary. “Brand of producer” and “Turbot” consistently show positive, significant effects in both countries, while “Ready to cook” and “Frozen” remain strongly negative. Minor cross-country differences reflect regional variation in preferences.

Overall, the MNL analysis confirms a strong preference for branded products and Turbot, and a clear aversion to processed formats like “Ready to cook” and “Frozen.” These findings highlight the product features most likely to influence consumer choice and should guide future marketing and product development strategies.

Estimated coefficients are also displayed as bar charts for the full sample and for each country, visualizing preferences by attribute level across groups.

Figure 3.5: Conditional Logit Model coefficients representing case study attributes

3.4 Relative importance of the attributes

Estimating the relative importance of product attributes is crucial to identifying the key drivers of consumer choice. This analysis supports strategic decisions on which features to prioritize for improved market alignment in Italy, Slovenia, and the combined sample.

Table 3.7 and Figure 3.6 compare the importance of five attributes—Preparation, Label, Specimen, Expiration Date, and Origin—across the three groups. Preparation is the most influential attribute in all cases, with significantly higher weights (General: 47.22%; Italy: 48.51%; Slovenia: 39.92%) than the others. Label and Specimen show moderate influence, while Expiration Date and Origin are less impactful. Slovenian respondents tend to assign higher importance across most attributes, though Preparation remains the dominant factor in all settings.

Table 3.7: Relative importance of seafood product attributes

Attribute	Relative Importance - General Model	Relative Importance - Italy	Relative Importance - Slovenia
Preparation	47.22%	48.51%	39.92%
Label	23.42%	32.75%	24.39%
Specimen	17.71%	16.42%	20.59%
Expiration date	6.21%	1.74%	8.31%
Origin	5.45%	0.58%	6.78%

Figure 3.6: Relative importance of seafood product attributes

3.5 Goodness of Fit

This section summarizes the Goodness of Fit (GOF) statistics for the MNL models estimated for the full sample and separately for Italy and Slovenia (Table 3.8). Rho-squared and adjusted rho-squared values indicate modest but meaningful explanatory power, with Slovenia showing the best fit. This is further supported by the lowest Akaike (AIC) and Bayesian (BIC) Information Criterion values in the Slovenian model, suggesting better balance between fit and model complexity. Each model estimates 12 coefficients, maintaining structural consistency. The improvement from the log-likelihood at start to the log-likelihood at convergence confirms that all models outperform the

null. Overall, results indicate acceptable model performance, with the Slovenian dataset demonstrating relatively superior fit.

Table 3.8: Multinomial logit model Goodness-of-Fit statistics

Model assessment statistics	General Model	Italy	Slovenia
Rho-squared	0.053	0.052	0.8
Adjusted rho-squared	0.40	0.025	0.05
Akaike information criterion (AIC)	1705.218	856.78	850.63
Bayesian information criterion (BIC)	1761.553	904.68	898.77
Number of coefficients	12	12	12
Log likelihood at start	-887.68	-439.44	-448.23
Log likelihood at convergence	-840.60	-416.39	-413.31

Additional model evaluation and hypothesis testing statistics—including the Concordance, Likelihood Ratio Test, Wald Test, and Score (logrank) Test—are summarized in [Table 3.9](#) for the general model and country-specific subsets. Concordance values range from 0.607 (Italy) to 0.658 (Slovenia), reflecting moderate to good predictive accuracy.

All three hypothesis tests show high test statistics with 11 degrees of freedom and p-values near zero across samples, confirming that the inclusion of explanatory variables significantly improves model fit. These results support the robustness and explanatory power of the MNL models.

Overall, the combination of satisfactory concordance values and highly significant hypothesis tests provides strong evidence that the MNL models fit the data well and effectively capture variations in respondents' preferences both within each country and across the combined dataset.

Table 3.9: Model evaluation and hypothesis testing statistics

Model evaluation and hypothesis testing statistics	General	Italy	Slovenia
Concordance	0.632 (s.e. = 0.019)	0.607 (s.e. = 0.027)	0.658 (s.e. = 0.026)
Likelihood ratio test	94.14 on 11 df, p=3e-15	46.1 on 11 df, p=3e-06	69.83 on 11 df, p=1e-10
Wald test	91.54 on 11 df, p=8e-15	44.89 on 11 df, p=5e-06	64.31 on 11 df, p=1e-09
Score (logrank) test	96.32 on 11 df, p=1e-15	47.29 on 11 df, p=2e-06	68.85 on 11 df, p=2e-10

Note: s.e.= standard error; df = degrees of freedom

3.6 Sensory evaluation

This section explores consumer behavior and seafood product evaluation, focusing on organoleptic characteristics. It is divided into two parts. The first, *Sensory Evaluation*, presents results from the expert panel's assessment of four fish products, offering objective profiles of their sensory attributes. The second, *Tasting Perceptions and Purchase Preferences*, reports participants' subjective tasting experiences and stated preferences, including purchase intentions. By combining consumer habits with both objective sensory data and subjective evaluations, this section offers a comprehensive view of the factors influencing seafood consumption.

3.6.1 Sensory Evaluation by a panel of experts

In the first phase of the sensory analysis, a panel of six expert assessors conducted a Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) to develop objective sensory profiles for the four selected seafood products: turbot, trout, seabream, and mussels. These profiles will serve as the basis for subsequent consumer preference mapping. The main sensory insights for each product, derived from expert evaluations and visualized in radar charts, are presented below.

The sensory profile of *Turbot* (Figure 3.7) is marked by subtle and refined characteristics. The most prominent attribute was a “*chicken breast*” aftertaste, suggesting a persistent, white-meat-like flavor. Moderate intensities were noted for *overall flavor*, *tenderness*, and *laminar structure*, while *saltiness*, *oiliness*, and *bitterness* were low—indicating a clean, mild taste with minimal fat perception. This positions turbot as a *neutral, non-fishy* option, likely to appeal to consumers preferring delicate flavors and soft textures. These findings support targeted marketing toward segments seeking milder seafood profiles.

Figure 3.7: Sensory profile of Turbot based on expert evaluation

Trout exhibited the most *intense* and *complex* sensory profile among the four products (Figure 3.8). Characterized by a *strong earthy flavor*, marked *brininess*, and a lingering *bitterness*. *Chewiness*, *moisture*, and *general flavor intensity* were also relatively high, reflecting a *rustic and robust character* likely linked to its freshwater origin. These attributes may appeal to consumers who favor bold, traditional flavors, but may deter those with neophobic or sensitive palates. Trout's distinct profile underscores its potential for market segmentation, to be further explored in consumer testing.

Figure 3.8: Sensory profile of Trout based on expert evaluation

Sea bream exhibited *balanced sensory attributes* (Figure 3.9). *Umami aftertaste* was the most prominent attribute, contributing to a rich, lingering savory impression. *High general flavor intensity* and moderate *brininess* created a clean, *full-bodied marine profile*. Texture attributes such as *tenderness* and *flakiness* were notable, while negative traits like *bitterness* and *oiliness* were minimal. This harmonious profile suggests strong consumer acceptance, appealing both to seafood enthusiasts and a broader audience seeking cohesive texture and mild flavors.

Figure 3.9: Sensory profile of Sea Bream based on expert evaluation

Mussels exhibited a distinctive sensory profile (Figure 3.10), with the highest intensity across all products for crustacean aroma, umami, brininess, and marine aftertaste. These traits define mussels as highly characterful and expressive. Structurally, high moisture, exudate, and turbidity contributed to a juicy mouthfeel but may pose visual or textural challenges for some consumers. The pronounced aftertaste reinforced their strong sensory identity. Mussels are likely to appeal to shellfish consumers and those seeking intense marine flavors, though texture and appearance may limit acceptance among more sensitive segments, warranting tailored communication strategies.

Figure 3.10: Sensory profile of Mussels based on expert evaluation

3.6.2 Tasting experience with consumers

To assess participants' perceptions, each seafood product—turbot, trout, sea bream, and mussels—was tasted individually. Following each tasting, participants answered three targeted questions, the first of which asked them to rate the product's overall liking on a scale from "extremely unpleasant" to "extremely pleasant." Results, illustrated in [Figure 3.11](#), indicate that turbot and sea bream were the most favored, with nearly 50% of respondents rating them as very pleasant. Negative or neutral evaluations for these products were minimal. Mussels also received generally positive ratings, though a small portion of participants reported dislike. Trout elicited the most diverse responses and emerged as the least preferred product in the sample.

Figure 3.11: Respondent ratings for the four products

For the second question, participants were asked: "Would you consider purchasing this product, assuming a normal price?" They indicated their purchase likelihood as a percentage. Results aligned with the liking scores: turbot and sea bream received the highest purchase intent, with most respondents indicating a likelihood of 60% or higher. For mussels, Slovenian participants more frequently selected an 80% likelihood ("I would probably buy it"), though overall responses were similar between countries. Trout showed the lowest purchase intent, particularly among Italian participants, while some Slovenians expressed greater interest ([Figure 3.12](#)).

Figure 3.12: Respondent stated purchasing likelihood

Finally, participants stated the maximum percentage they would be willing to pay above the current price for each product. A value of 0% indicated willingness to pay the current price, negative values reflected a desire to pay less, and positive values a willingness to pay more.

Most respondents selected 0%, showing a general preference for paying the standard price. Sea bream stood out, with many willing to pay 5% to 20% more. Turbot followed in popularity, though fewer participants were willing to pay a premium compared to sea bream. Mussel responses were more varied, reflecting mixed perceptions. Trout received the lowest WTP values overall (Figure 3.13).

Figure 3.13: Respondent willingness to pay (WTP)

3.7. Drivers and barriers to aquaculture fish consumption

This paragraph synthesizes the key factors that influence consumer acceptance of the four seafood products. By integrating findings from the sensory tasting study and the Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE), it highlights the main drivers and barriers shaping aquaculture product consumption in Italy and Slovenia.

3.7.1 Main Drivers

The first identified drivers of consumer choice were product *branding* and *recognizability*. The presence of a producer brand was the strongest positive predictor in the MNL model, reflecting *trust* and *perceived quality assurance*. Regarding *preferred species*, and *familiarity* turbot and sea bream consistently emerged as the most favored in both choice models and tasting tests, combining *familiarity* with *perceived quality* to strongly motivate preference and purchase intent. Sensory characteristics also played a key role: consumers particularly appreciated *delicate, well-balanced flavor profiles*, such as turbot's "chicken breast" aftertaste and sea bream's umami richness. Texture attributes like *tenderness* and *flakiness* in sea bream, as well as *moisture* noted in trout and mussels, enhanced mouthfeel and supported positive evaluations and purchase willingness. *Label* and *sustainability* claims had a limited influence on choice. While no specific label stood out strongly, consumers showed moderate interest in product certification and traceability. Finally, *cultural familiarity* influenced preferences, with trout enjoying relatively

higher acceptance among Slovenian participants, likely due to habitual consumption and regional taste norms.

3.7.2. Main barriers

The main barriers relate to *degree of processing* and *freshness perception*: processed forms like *Ready to cook* and *Frozen* were strongly disliked compared to *Whole cleaned* showing a preference for fresh, minimally processed fish. Sensory barriers include *strong or earthy flavors*, especially in trout, which was least liked—particularly by Italians—due to its earthy, bitter, and briny notes. Such intense traits deter sensitive or neophobic consumers. *Bitterness* and *aftertaste* in trout and mussels negatively affected liking and willingness to pay. For mussels, factors like *exudate*, *turbidity*, and *high moisture* were viewed negatively by experts, indicating texture can both attract or repel depending on consumer preferences.

Price sensitivity was a notable barrier. Despite strong appreciation, turbot and sea bream had limited willingness to pay a premium, with most respondents choosing no price increase, reflecting value-for-money concerns for high-end species. Additionally, varied consumer reactions to trout and mussels suggest that broad-market positioning may lead to rejection of strongly flavored products, highlighting the challenge of diverse preferences.

4. Conclusions

This report presents findings from a choice experiment involving 101 adult consumers (aged 18–65) in Italy (n=50) and Slovenia (n=51), aimed at understanding attitudes and preferences toward seafood, with an emphasis on aquaculture products. The study employed a mixed-method approach combining a virtual Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) and sensory analysis conducted by both expert panelists and participants. Participants were generally young (mean age ~34 years) with medium income levels; half were primarily responsible for family food purchases. Most reported purchasing seafood and aquaculture products several times weekly or monthly, though a notable share never purchased aquaculture items.

The DCE data were analyzed using a Multinomial Logit model (MNL) based on 2,424 possible choice combinations and 808 recorded choices. Goodness-of-fit statistics indicated the best model fit for Slovenia, with Rho-squared values ranging from 0.607 (Italy) to 0.658 (Slovenia). Likelihood Ratio, Wald, and Score tests confirmed the statistical significance and predictive power of the models.

Among the five product attributes examined—Preparation, Label, Specimen, Expiration Date, and Origin—Preparation consistently ranked highest in importance across samples. Brand of producer and Turbot species had the strongest positive effects on choice, whereas “Ready to cook” and “Frozen” preparations were strongly disfavored compared to whole cleaned fish. Expert sensory evaluation characterized turbot as subtle and refined, trout as intense and complex, sea bream as balanced and savory, and mussels as highly distinctive with strong marine flavors and variable textural appeal. Consumer tasting aligned with these profiles: turbot and sea bream were widely liked, mussels received mixed but generally positive reactions, and trout was the least preferred.

Purchase intentions and willingness-to-pay (WTP) premiums reflected these preferences. Sea bream commanded the highest WTP (5%–20% above baseline), followed by turbot, while mussels showed variable WTP and trout had the lowest or negative premiums.

Integrating objective sensory data with subjective preferences offers valuable insights into seafood consumption drivers and barriers, supporting targeted marketing and product development. Limitations include underrepresentation of lower-income and older consumers, suggesting future research should focus on these groups to enhance generalizability.

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Appendix 1: Two-Dimensional Representations of Products and Labels Included in the Virtual DCE

Italy

Sea bream

Whole raw fish	Fresh, clean fillets	Frozen fillets	Ready to cook

Turbot

Whole raw fish	Fresh, clean fillets	Frozen fillets	Ready to cook

Trout

Whole raw fish	Fresh, clean fillets	Frozen fillets	Ready to cook

Mussels

Whole raw shellfish	Fresh, clean shellfish	Frozen	Ready to cook

Slovenia

Sea bream

Whole raw fish	Fresh, clean fillets	Frozen fillets	Ready to cook

Turbot

Whole raw fish	Fresh, clean fillets	Frozen fillets	Ready to cook

Trout

Whole raw fish	Fresh, clean fillets	Frozen fillets	Ready to cook

Mussels

Whole raw shellfish	Fresh, clean shellfish	Frozen	Ready to cook

Labels

Organic	Sustainable Aquaculture	Certified Supply Chain	Brand of the Producer

Appendix 2: Results from Sensory Analysis with Consumers

Sea Bream

Try the sample and indicate on the following scale how much you liked it:						
	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
Extremely unpleasant	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Very unpleasant	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Moderately unpleasant	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
Slightly unpleasant	2	1.98%	1	2%	1	1.96%
Neutral	7	6.93%	1	2%	6	11.76%
Slightly pleasant	4	3.96%	2	4%	2	3.92%
Moderately pleasant	11	10.89%	7	14%	4	7.84%
Very pleasant	47	46.53%	28	56%	19	37.25%
Extremely pleasant	29	28.71%	11	22%	18	35.29%

Please indicate below if you would like to purchase this product, assuming it is priced normally:						
	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
I would almost certainly NOT purchase it" (1% likelihood)	2	1.98%	0	0%	2	3.92%
There is a very slight chance I would buy it" (10% likelihood)	3	2.97%	2	4%	1	1.96%
There is a small chance I would buy it" (20% likelihood)	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
There is some chance I would buy it" (30% likelihood)	2	1.98%	1	2%	1	1.96%
There is a fair chance I would buy it" (40% likelihood)	4	3.96%	0	0%	4	7.84%
I am equally likely to buy or not buy it" (50% likelihood)	7	6.93%	3	6%	4	7.84%
There is a good chance I would buy it" (60% likelihood)	13	12.87%	7	14%	6	11.76%
I would probably buy it" (70% likelihood)	7	6.93%	3	6%	4	7.84%
I would very likely buy it" (80% likelihood)	18	17.82%	12	24%	6	11.76%
I would almost certainly buy it" (90% likelihood)	20	19.80%	13	26%	7	13.73%
I am virtually certain I would buy it" (99% likelihood)	24	23.76%	9	18%	15	29.41%

What is the maximum percentage more you would be willing to pay for this product?
(0% means you'd pay the same as current price, negative percentages indicate you'd pay less, and positive percentages mean you'd pay more for it.)

	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
-30% or less	4	3.96%	0	0%	4	7.84%
-25%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
-20%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
-15%	2	1.98%	1	2%	1	1.96%
-10%	3	2.97%	1	2%	2	3.92%
-5%	2	1.98%	1	2%	1	1.96%
0%	26	25.74%	13	26%	13	25.49%
+5%	24	23.76%	14	28%	10	19.61%
+10%	13	12.87%	8	16%	5	9.80%
+15%	13	12.87%	9	18%	4	7.84%
+20%	11	10.89%	2	4%	9	17.65%
+25%	1	0.99%	1	2%	0	0%
+30% or more	2	1.98%	0	0%	2	3.92%

Trout

Try the sample and indicate on the following scale how much you liked it:						
	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
Extremely unpleasant	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Very unpleasant	4	3.96%	2	4%	2	3.92%
Moderately unpleasant	6	5.94%	5	10%	1	1.96%
Slightly unpleasant	17	16.83%	10	20%	7	13.73%
Neutral	16	15.84%	9	18%	7	13.73%
Slightly pleasant	18	17.82%	9	18%	9	17.65%
Moderately pleasant	23	22.77%	8	16%	15	29.41%
Very pleasant	13	12.87%	5	10%	8	15.69%
Extremely pleasant	4	3.96%	2	4%	2	3.92%

Please indicate below if you would like to purchase this product, assuming it is priced normally:						
	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
I would almost certainly NOT purchase it" (1% likelihood)	6	5.94%	3	6%	3	5.88%
There is a very slight chance I would buy it" (10% likelihood)	14	13.86%	10	20%	4	7.84%
There is a small chance I would buy it" (20% likelihood)	21	20.79%	15	30%	6	11.76%
There is some chance I would buy it" (30% likelihood)	10	9.90%	8	16%	2	3.92%
There is a fair chance I would buy it" (40% likelihood)	7	6.93%	3	6%	4	7.84%
I am equally likely to buy or not buy it" (50% likelihood)	12	11.88%	5	10%	7	13.73%
There is a good chance I would buy it" (60% likelihood)	9	8.91%	1	2%	8	15.69%
I would probably buy it" (70% likelihood)	6	5.94%	0	0%	6	11.76%
I would very likely buy it" (80% likelihood)	8	7.92%	4	8%	4	7.84%
I would almost certainly buy it" (90% likelihood)	4	3.96%	1	2%	3	5.88%
I am virtually certain I would buy it" (99% likelihood)	4	3.96%	0	0%	4	7.84%

What is the maximum percentage more you would be willing to pay for this product?
 (0% means you'd pay the same as current price, negative percentages indicate you'd pay less, and positive percentages mean you'd pay more for it.)

	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
-30% or less	7	6.93%	3	6%	4	7.84%
-25%	4	3.96%	2	4%	2	3.92%
-20%	5	4.95%	5	10%	0	0%
-15%	11	10.89%	7	14%	4	7.84%
-10%	12	11.88%	8	16%	4	7.84%
-5%	9	8.91%	5	10%	4	7.84%
0%	39	38.61%	16	32%	23	45.10%
+5%	3	2.97%	0	0%	3	5.88%
+10%	4	3.96%	2	4%	2	3.92%
+15%	3	2.97%	2	4%	1	1.96%
+20%	2	1.98%	0	0%	2	3.92%
+25%	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
+30% or more	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%

Mussels:

Try the sample and indicate on the following scale how much you liked it:

	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
Extremely unpleasant	1	0.99%	1	2%	0	0%
Very unpleasant	3	2.97%	3	6%	0	0%
Moderately unpleasant	4	3.96%	1	2%	3	5.88%
Slightly unpleasant	7	6.93%	4	8%	3	5.88%
Neutral	6	5.94%	2	4%	4	7.84%
Slightly pleasant	16	15.84%	10	20%	6	11.76%
Moderately pleasant	20	19.80%	11	22%	9	17.65%
Very pleasant	28	27.72%	11	22%	17	33.33%
Extremely pleasant	16	15.84%	7	14%	9	17.65%

Please indicate below if you would like to purchase this product, assuming it is priced normally:

	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
I would almost certainly NOT purchase it" (1% likelihood)	6	5.94%	4	8%	2	3.92%
There is a very slight chance I would buy it" (10% likelihood)	9	8.91%	4	8%	5	9.80%
There is a small chance I would buy it" (20% likelihood)	8	7.92%	3	6%	5	9.80%
There is some chance I would buy it" (30% likelihood)	8	7.92%	5	10%	3	5.88%
There is a fair chance I would buy it" (40% likelihood)	6	5.94%	3	6%	3	5.88%
I am equally likely to buy or not buy it" (50% likelihood)	7	6.93%	2	4%	5	9.80%
There is a good chance I would buy it" (60% likelihood)	10	9.90%	7	14%	3	5.88%
I would probably buy it" (70% likelihood)	7	6.93%	5	10%	2	3.92%
I would very likely buy it" (80% likelihood)	18	17.82%	7	14%	11	21.57%
I would almost certainly buy it" (90% likelihood)	10	9.90%	5	10%	5	9.80%
I am virtually certain I would buy it" (99% likelihood)	12	11.88%	5	10%	7	13.73%

What is the maximum percentage more you would be willing to pay for this product?
 (0% means you'd pay the same as current price, negative percentages indicate you'd pay less, and positive percentages mean you'd pay more for it.)

	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
-30% or less	2	1.98%	0	0%	2	3.92%
-25%	4	3.96%	3	6%	1	1.96%
-20%	3	2.97%	2	4%	1	1.96%
-15%	4	3.96%	1	2%	3	5.88%
-10%	6	5.94%	5	10%	1	1.96%
-5%	8	7.92%	4	8%	4	7.84%
0%	35	34.65%	20	20%	15	29.41%
+5%	17	16.83%	9	18%	8	15.69%
+10%	9	8.91%	1	2%	8	15.69%
+15%	5	4.95%	4	8%	1	1.96%
+20%	6	5.94%	1	2%	5	9.80%
+25%	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
+30% or more	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%

Turbot:

Try the sample and indicate on the following scale how much you liked it:						
	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
Extremely unpleasant	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Very unpleasant	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Moderately unpleasant	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
Slightly unpleasant	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Neutral	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
Slightly pleasant	8	7.92%	5	10%	3	5.88%
Moderately pleasant	32	31.68%	19	38%	13	25.49%
Very pleasant	45	44.55%	22	44%	23	45.10%
Extremely pleasant	14	13.86%	4	8%	10	19.61%

Please indicate below if you would like to purchase this product, assuming it is priced normally:						
	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
I would almost certainly NOT purchase it" (1% likelihood)	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
There is a very slight chance I would buy it" (10% likelihood)	2	1.98%	2	4%	0	0%
There is a small chance I would buy it" (20% likelihood)	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
There is some chance I would buy it" (30% likelihood)	5	4.95%	2	4%	3	5.88%
There is a fair chance I would buy it" (40% likelihood)	5	4.95%	4	8%	1	1.96%
I am equally likely to buy or not buy it" (50% likelihood)	9	8.91%	3	6%	6	11.76%
There is a good chance I would buy it" (60% likelihood)	18	17.82%	11	22%	7	13.73%
I would probably buy it" (70% likelihood)	19	18.81%	11	22%	8	15.69%
I would very likely buy it" (80% likelihood)	16	15.84%	8	16%	8	15.69%
I would almost certainly buy it" (90% likelihood)	12	11.88%	4	8%	8	15.69%
I am virtually certain I would buy it" (99% likelihood)	13	12.87%	5	10%	8	15.69%

What is the maximum percentage more you would be willing to pay for this product?
 (0% means you'd pay the same as current price, negative percentages indicate you'd pay less, and positive percentages mean you'd pay more for it.)

	General (n = 101)		Italy (n = 50)		Slovenia (n = 51)	
-30% or less	2	1.98%	0	0%	2	3.92%
-25%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
-20%	1	0.99%	0	0%	1	1.96%
-15%	2	1.98%	0	0%	2	3.92%
-10%	7	6.93%	3	6%	4	7.84%
-5%	2	1.98%	2	4%	0	0%
0%	41	40.59%	25	50%	16	31.37%
+5%	15	14.85%	9	18%	6	11.76%
+10%	18	17.82%	7	14%	11	21.57%
+15%	11	10.89%	3	6%	8	15.69%
+20%	2	1.98%	1	2%	1	1.96%
+25%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
+30% or more	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%

